

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN MATHEMATICS AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15390508>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to explore the relationship between motivation and academic performance in Mathematics among Grade 9 students at Butong, Quezon, Bukidnon. Employing a quantitative correlational research design, the study gathered data from 35 randomly selected students using a Mathematics Motivation Scale Questionnaire adopted from Redoble (2020) and analyzed their third-quarter grades. Descriptive statistics were used to determine the students' level of motivation and academic performance, while Pearson's r correlation was applied to examine the relationship between the two variables. Results revealed that students' academic performance in Mathematics was at a "Very Satisfactory" level with a mean score of 86. Their overall motivation was assessed as moderate, with a mean score of 3.24, highlighting strong motivation toward understanding and valuing mathematics content but also revealing emotional factors. Moreover, results showed a significant moderate positive relationship between students' motivation and academic performance, indicating that higher motivation is associated with better academic outcomes, although it is not the sole determinant. These findings are consistent with previous local and international studies, reinforcing the role of motivation in fostering improved academic performance. The study recommends that educators implement strategies that not only enhance students' engagement and perceived relevance of mathematics but also address emotional factors to maximize learning outcomes.

Keywords: *academic performance, motivation, mathematics*

INTRODUCTION

Academic success has long been recognized as an important factor in shaping an individual's future opportunities, career paths, and personal development. Among the numerous determinants of academic performance, motivation emerges as one of the most influential yet complex factors (Deci & Ryan, 2000). Motivation, defined as the internal process that initiates, directs, and sustains goal-oriented behavior, is essential in educational settings where persistence, effort, and engagement are essential for success (Schunk et al., 2008).

Research indicates that highly motivated students are more likely to exhibit behaviors associated with academic achievement, such as sustained attention, effective study habits, and resilience in the face of challenges (Ryan & Deci, 2017). Walker et al. (2024) emphasize that supporting students' intrinsic motivation, engaging in activities for inherent satisfaction, has consistently positive effects on academic performance. In contrast, extrinsic motivation, driven by external rewards or pressures, shows mixed effects on performance.

Another study by Iqbal et al., (2023) investigates the effects of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on higher education performance, mediated by quality culture. The findings reveal that intrinsic motivation and quality culture significantly impact higher education performance. While extrinsic motivation influences quality culture, its direct effect on higher education performance is not empirically supported. This suggests that intrinsic motivation plays an important role in enhancing academic outcomes.

Research by Liu et al., (2024) explores the relationships among psychological capital, learning motivation, emotional engagement, and academic performance in a blended learning environment. The study finds that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation impact academic performance, with intrinsic motivation mediating the relationship between extrinsic motivation and academic outcomes. This shows the importance of fostering intrinsic motivation to enhance learning effectiveness.

Several studies emphasize that motivation does not operate in isolation but interacts with other psychological, social, and contextual factors that influence academic performance (Eccles & Wigfield, 2002). For instance, the expectancy-value theory posits that students' beliefs about their abilities and the value they attach to academic tasks critically affect their motivation and, consequently, their performance (Wigfield & Eccles, 2000). In addition, self-determination theory highlights that an environment supporting autonomy, competence, and relatedness fosters more self-regulated forms of motivation, which are positively linked to academic success (Deci & Ryan, 2000).

Motivation influences how much effort students are willing to put into their studies, how they manage challenges, and how they stay committed to reaching their goals. Given the essential role that motivation plays in shaping academic performance, understanding its dynamics is essential for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders aiming to enhance student achievement. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the relationship between motivation and academic performance, examining how different levels whether

high, moderate, or low of motivation correlate with students' academic outcomes among Grade 9 students. Through this, the study hopes to provide useful insights that can help teachers and school leaders create strategies and programs that foster stronger motivation among students to improve their academic performance.

Research Questions

The study's primary purpose was to assess the factors that affect academic performance in mathematics. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of students' academic performance in Mathematics?
2. What is the level of students' motivation in learning Mathematics?
3. Is there a significant relationship between students' motivation and their academic performance in Mathematics?

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted with Grade 9 junior high school students located in Butong, Quezon, Bukidnon. The research setting provided a suitable environment to gather data from participants regarding their motivation and academic performance of the students. The participants of this study consisted of 35 Grade 9 junior high school students, included both males and females. The sample was selected through random sampling to ensure that every student within the target population had an equal chance of being included. Random sampling minimized selection bias and ensured that the sample represented the larger population of Grade 9 students. The researcher personally administered the survey questionnaires to the respondents during their free periods to avoid disrupting their academic activities. Prior to distribution, the researcher provided a brief orientation regarding the purpose of the study and assured the participants of confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. The students were given ample time to complete the survey, and the completed questionnaires were collected immediately afterward to ensure a high response rate and the integrity of the data.

The study utilized a mathematics motivation survey questionnaire adopted from Redoble (2020). The Mathematics Motivation Scale Questionnaire is composed of 26 questions. The items for this questionnaire were validated and underwent a reliability test with a Cronbach alpha of 0.887.

Scale	Range	Descriptive Rating	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.51-5.0	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.51-4.5	Agree	High
3	2.51-3.5	Undecided	Moderate
2	1.51-2.5	Disagree	Low
1	1-1.5	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

The third quarter grades of the students in Mathematics, examined using frequency counts and percentages, are interpreted based on the Department of Education (DepEd) grading system in the Philippines. This grading scale is outlined in DepEd Order No. 8, s. 2015, also known as the Policy Guidelines on Classroom Assessment for the K to 12 Basic Education Program.

Grade Range	Qualitative Description
90-100	Outstanding (O)
85-89	Very Satisfactory (VS)
80-84	Satisfactory (S)
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
74 and below	Did Not Meet Expectation (DNME)

The data collected were analyzed using the following statistical treatments: descriptive statistics, including mean, frequency, and standard deviation, were used to describe the respondents' academic performance and motivation. A Pearson R Correlation was used to determine the relationship between students' motivation and academic performance.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Academic Performance

Table 1. Academic Performance of the Students in Mathematics

Academic Performance			
Grade Range	Frequency	Percentage	Qualitative Interpretation
90-100	12	34.29%	Outstanding
85-89	11	31.43%	Very Satisfactory
80-84	7	20%	Satisfactory
75-79	2	5.71%	Fairly Satisfactory
74 and below	3	8.57%	Did Not Meet Expectation
Mean	86		Very Satisfactory

As shown in table 1, the academic performance of the students in mathematics has a mean of 86, indicating a "very satisfactory". This means that the students meet expectations and go beyond the passing grade which implies that these students are knowledgeable on the subject matter.

This result is inconsistent with the findings of Basco (2020), which revealed that a significant number of students scored within the range of 75 to 79. Such scores, although passing, are relatively low and raise a genuine concern for teachers regarding the students' level of mastery and understanding of the subject matter. Basco's study highlights the need for greater attention and intervention to address gaps in students' academic achievement. It suggests that without timely and appropriate support, students may continue to perform at marginal levels, potentially affecting their future academic

pursuits and overall confidence in the subject. By fostering a culture of academic excellence and continuous improvement, it is possible to ensure that students not only meet the basic requirements but also develop a deeper understanding and appreciation of their academic subjects.

Mathematics Motivation

Table 2. Level of Students' Mathematics Motivation

INDICATOR	Mean	Qualitative Interpretation
My biggest wish is to understand the content of the learning material used in the math class.	3.89	H
I feel the learning materials used in math class are useful.	3.83	H
I am interested in the learning material in math class.	3.80	H
What I learn in the math class can be apply in my daily life.	3.71	H
If I have correct learning pattern to learn math, I will learn better in the class.	3.57	H
The skills I learn from the math class can be applied in other classes.	3.54	H
If I study hard enough, I can understand the content of the learning materials used in math class.	3.54	H
I like every topics and contents in math class.	3.49	H
To me, take math class can improve my overall academy score.	3.46	H
To get better score in math, I will learn harder.	3.46	H
I would like to have curiosity-initials materials in math class even they are quite difficult.	3.34	M
In math class, I would like to have more projects and homework which will help me learn more, even though these will not improve my scores.	3.34	M
I believe that I can master every topic in math class.	3.26	M
I want to get higher scores in math class, because I want to demonstrate my capability to my classmates.	3.23	M
As for math, I am competent to teach other my classmates.	3.23	M
I believe that I will have excellent math grades in math class.	3.11	M
I hope I can get higher grade in math than any other classmates.	3.11	M
I want to get other people's recognition so I want higher scores in math class.	3.09	M
Mathematics contributes a lot to whole human beings.	3.06	M
In math class, I would like to have some challenging materials and they will make me learn more.	3.00	M
In taking math exam, I will have negative thought that I am inferior than other classmates. **	2.86	M
In taking math exam, I would think about the consequence of failing in the exam. **	2.80	M
If I do not learn better in the math class, I believe it is my fault. **	2.77	M
I believe that I can understand the most difficult part in the math materials by my own.	2.63	M
In taking math exam, my heart beat faster. **	2.60	L
Math is not difficult to me.	2.54	L
MEAN	3.24	M

***Negative Indicators (Scoring is reversed)*

Legend:

Scale	Range	Qualitative Interpretation
5	4.21-5.0	Very High (VH)
4	3.41-4.20	High (H)
3	2.61-3.40	Moderate (M)
2	1.81-2.60	Low (L)
1	1-1.80	Very Low (VL)

As shown in table 2, the students' overall motivation toward learning mathematics is at a moderate level, with a mean score of 3.24. Among all the indicators, the top two highest mean scores are: "My biggest wish is to understand the content of the learning material used in the math class" with a mean of 3.89, and "I feel the learning materials used in math class are useful" with a mean of 3.83. These results indicate a strong intrinsic motivation, where students are driven by a desire to understand and find value in what they are learning. On the other hand, the two lowest mean scores are: "Math is not difficult to me" with a mean of 2.54, and "In taking math exams, my heart beats faster" with a mean of 2.60. These suggest that many students find math challenging and experience anxiety during assessments, reflecting emotional barriers that may hinder their motivation and performance.

The data implies that students are primarily motivated by a genuine desire to understand and find value in mathematics, highlighting a strong motivation. However, their moderate overall motivation level, combined with signs of math anxiety and perceived difficulty, suggests that emotional factors are limiting their full engagement. This means that to boost students' overall motivation and learning outcomes, educators should not only focus on making math content meaningful but also address students' emotional experiences, especially by reducing anxiety and building confidence in their math abilities.

Several studies have shown that motivation has a moderate relationship with academic performance. Richardson and Bond (2012) conducted a meta-analysis and found that motivation-related constructs, such as self-efficacy and intrinsic motivation, were moderately correlated with academic performance. Similarly, Robbins et al. (2004) reported that motivation exhibited moderate predictive validity toward college outcomes, reinforcing the idea that while motivation is important, it is not the sole determinant of academic success. Sipin and Paglinawan (2024) highlighted that motivation and creativity were strongly linked and that students with higher motivation demonstrated improved academic outcomes. The consistent findings across various local contexts highlight that enhancing students' motivation, particularly their intrinsic motivation to understand and appreciate mathematics, can lead to meaningful improvements in their academic performance.

Table 3. Correlation Between the Mathematics Motivation and Academic Performance of Students

		Academic Performance	Motivation
Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.443
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.008**
	N	35	35
Motivation	Pearson Correlation	.443	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.008**	
	N	35	

** correlation is highly significant at 0.01 level

Table 3 shows the results of the Pearson correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant moderate positive relationship between motivation and academic performance among the participants ($r = .443$, $p = .008$, $N = 35$). This indicates that higher levels of motivation are associated with better academic performance. The p -value of .008, which is less than the standard significance level of 0.01, suggests that the correlation is highly significant and not likely due to chance. It indicates that motivation plays an important role in influencing academic performance. As students' motivation increases, there is a tendency for their academic achievements to improve. However, the correlation is moderate, meaning that while motivation is an important factor, other variables may also contribute to students' academic outcomes.

This finding conformed to the study of Sabanal et al. (2023), which revealed that the students' motivation towards learning and academic performance were positively and significantly correlated. While this study already found high motivation and very satisfactory academic performance among students, the researchers still recommend raising them to very high and outstanding levels, respectively. Similarly, Sipin and Paglinawan, (2024) results showed positive levels of creativity and motivation among students, with a strong positive correlation, indicating that higher creativity corresponds to greater motivation. Moreover, the study of Khaneghahi (2022) showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between academic motivation and students' academic enthusiasm. The intensity of this relationship is very strong, and academic motivation has the power to predict academic enthusiasm, which therefore leads to good academic performance. Thus, Sabanal et al. (2023) reported a positive and significant relationship between motivation and academic performance among junior high school students in Mindanao, noting that students with greater motivation consistently achieved higher in mathematics assessments.

Conclusions

The findings revealed that the students' academic performance in mathematics was at a very satisfactory level, with a mean score of 86. This indicates that most of the students meet or exceed the academic expectations, demonstrating a good understanding of mathematical concepts.

Regarding the students' level of motivation, results showed an overall moderate motivation, with a mean of 3.24. Students exhibited strong intrinsic motivation, particularly in their desire to understand and find relevance in the learning materials. However,

emotional factors such as math anxiety and perceptions of difficulty were also evident, suggesting potential barriers to achieving higher levels of engagement and performance.

The study revealed a significant moderate positive relationship between students' motivation and academic performance ($r = .443$, $p = .008$). This indicates that higher motivation is associated with better academic performance, although other factors beyond motivation also contribute to students' success.

Recommendations

Based study's findings, the following recommendations are proposed for educators, policymakers, and educational institutions.

It is recommended that educators, administrators, and policymakers implement strategies to enhance student motivation. Programs that adhere motivation, such as goal-setting workshops, mentorship programs, and recognition of academic achievements, could be particularly beneficial. Additionally, creating a supportive and engaging learning environment that connects academic content to students' interests and future aspirations may further boost motivation and, in turn, improve academic performance. It is also recommended that future research explore other factors that may influence academic success, such as study habits, self-efficacy, and classroom environment, to develop a more comprehensive support framework for students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors of this study declare full compliance with ethical standards in the conduct of the research. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring that they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and potential risks. Participants were informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

Anonymity was maintained throughout the research process, with no identifying information collected. The respondents' well-being was safeguarded, and all measures were taken to minimize any potential harm.

Furthermore, no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the study, and the authors adhered to ethical research practices by strictly avoiding plagiarism. The interpretation of findings was free from bias, and the results were used exclusively for academic and research purposes.

Acknowledgments

The researcher extends sincere gratitude to the Science Education Department at the College of Education, Apyao National High School, and Central Mindanao University for their invaluable support and resources throughout this study. Their guidance and assistance were instrumental in the successful completion of this research. Additionally, the researcher is deeply appreciative of the unwavering support from family and friends,

whose encouragement and understanding provided the motivation needed to overcome the challenges encountered during this research journey.

REFERENCES

- Basco, R. O. (2020). Effectiveness of Song, Drill and Game Strategy in Improving Mathematical Performance. *International Educational Research*, 3(2), p1-p1.
- Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The “what” and “why” of goal pursuits: Human needs and the self-determination of behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268. https://doi.org/10.1207/S15327965PLI1104_01
- Eccles, J. S., & Wigfield, A. (2002). Motivational beliefs, values, and goals. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53, 109–132. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.psych.53.100901.135153>
- Iqbal, S., Razalli, M. R., & Taib, C. A. B. (2023). Influence of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation on higher education performance: Mediating effect of quality culture. *Frontiers in Education*, 8, Article 1099415. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2023.1099415>
- Khaneghahi, Sophia & Sefatgol, Sajad & Siyasar, Malihe. (2022). Investigating the Relationship between School Culture and Academic Enthusiasm with Academic Hope and Motivation in High School Students. *Journal of Social, Humanity, and Education*. 3. 29-41. 10.35912/jshe.v3i1.940.
- Liu, Y., Ma, S., & Chen, Y. (2024). The impacts of learning motivation, emotional engagement, and psychological capital on academic performance in a blended learning university course. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 15, Article 1357936. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1357936PMC+3>
- Redoble, S. (2020). Development and Validation of a Mathematics Motivation Scale for Junior High School Students. Unpublished Master’s Thesis.
- Redoble, S. (2020). Mathematics Motivation Scale Questionnaire: Development and validation. Unpublished thesis, Mindanao State University – Iligan Institute of Technology.
- Richardson, M., Abraham, C., & Bond, R. (2012). Psychological correlates of university students’ academic performance: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 138(2), 353–387. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0026838>
- Robbins, S. B., Lauver, K., Le, H., Davis, D., Langley, R., & Carlstrom, A. (2004). Do psychosocial and study skill factors predict college outcomes? A meta-analysis. *Psychological Bulletin*, 130(2), 261–288. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.130.2.261>
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2017). Self-determination theory: Basic psychological needs in motivation, development, and wellness. The Guilford Press. <https://doi.org/10.1521/978.14625/28806>.
- Sabanal, J. A., Reputana, G. D., Palwa, S. S., Lolinette, C., & Alimbon, J. A. (2023). Motivation and Academic Performance of Secondary Students in Science: A Correlational Study. *Asian Journal of Science Education*, 5(2), 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.24815/ajse.v5i2.31668>
- Sabanal, J. A., Reputana, G. D., Palwa, S. S., Lolinette, C., & Alimbon, J. A. (2023). Motivation and Academic Performance of Secondary Students in Science: A Correlational Study. *Asian Journal of Science Education*, 5(2), 20–29. <https://doi.org/10.24815/ajse.v5i2.31668>
- Schunk, D. H., Pintrich, P. R., & Meece, J. L. (2008). *Motivation in education: Theory, research, and applications* (3rd ed.). Pearson/Merrill Prentice Hall.
- Sipin, K., & Paglinawan, J. L. (2024). Mathematics Creativity and Motivation in Learning of Senior High School Students Using Quipper. *International Journal of All Research*

- Education & Scientific Methods, 6(6), 282–288.
<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/38729581>
- Sipin, Kim & Paglinawan, James. (2024). MATHEMATICS CREATIVITY AND MOTIVATION IN LEARNING OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS USING QUIPPER. International Journal of All Research Education & Scientific Methods. 6. 282-288.
- Walker, J., Smith, A., & Johnson, L. (2024). Exploring the relationship between motivation and academic performance among online and blended learners. Online Learning Journal, 28(1), 45–60. <https://olj.onlinelearningconsortium.org/index.php/olj/article/view/4602>
- Wigfield, A., & Eccles, J. S. (2000). Expectancy–value theory of achievement motivation. Contemporary Educational Psychology, 25(1), 68–81.
<https://doi.org/10.1006/ceps.1999.1015>.